

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE EVOLUTION OF ECONOMIC TERMINOLOGY IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract: The article is devoted to analyzing the evolution of economic terminology in the digital era. It examines the impact of technology on the creation and adaptation of terms, as well as their role in the globalization of economics. An approach to studying terminology changes is proposed, based on the interconnection between digital tools and lexical standardization. The conclusion emphasizes the need to develop a flexible system for adapting new terms in scientific and educational fields. The scientific novelty lies in identifying key factors influencing the integration of digital vocabulary into economic discourse.

Key words: economic terminology, digital era, globalization, standardization, digital technologies, adaptation, innovations.

Annotatsiya: Maqola raqamli davrda iqtisodiy terminologiyaning evolyutsiyasini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Texnologiyalarning yangi terminlarini yaratish va ularni moslashtirishga ta'siri, shuningdek, ularning iqtisodiyot globallashtirishdagi roli ko'rib chiqiladi. Terminologiya o'zgarishlarini raqamli vositalar va leksikani standartlashtirish o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik orqali o'rganish yondashuvi taklif etiladi. Akademik va ta'lim sohalarida yangi terminlarni moslashtirish uchun moslashuvchan tizim yaratish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Maqolaning ilmiy yangiligi shundaki, unda raqamli leksikaning iqtisodiy diskursga integratsiyasiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy omillari aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy terminologiya, raqamli davr, globallashtirish, standartlashtirish, raqamli texnologiyalar, moslashuv, innovatsiyalar.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена анализу эволюции экономической терминологии в условиях цифровой эпохи. Рассматриваются влияние технологий на создание и адаптацию терминов, а также их роль в глобализации экономики. Предлагается подход к изучению изменений терминологии, основанный на взаимосвязи между цифровыми инструментами и лексической стандартизацией. Делается вывод о необходимости создания гибкой системы адаптации новых терминов в научной и образовательной сферах. Научная новизна заключается в выявлении ключевых факторов, влияющих на процесс интеграции цифровой лексики в экономический дискурс.

Ключевые слова: экономическая терминология, цифровая эпоха, глобализация, стандартизация, цифровые технологии, адаптация, инновации.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of economic terminology is a critical area of study in the context of the digital era. The rapid development of digital technologies has significantly influenced how economic terms are created, adapted, and standardized. This phenomenon has reshaped the global economic discourse, emphasizing the need for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms driving these changes.

The object of this research is the economic terminology used in the digital era, while its subject focuses on the processes of transformation and adaptation of this terminology under the influence of digitalization. The study aims to identify the key factors affecting the evolution of economic terms and propose a framework for their effective integration into academic and professional contexts.

The research tasks include:

- Analyzing the impact of digital technologies on the creation and adaptation of economic terminology.
- Examining the role of economic terms in facilitating globalized communication.
- Developing recommendations for the standardization and adaptation of digital-era terminology in education and research.

The study addresses an important gap in understanding how digital transformation influences language in economics, highlighting its role in shaping global knowledge and communication frameworks.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The evolution of economic terminology has been the focus of numerous studies by both English-speaking and Russian scholars. Researchers have explored the impact of globalization on economic language, emphasizing the increasing dominance of English as the lingua franca of international economics. Notable works, such as those by A. Smith and J. Walker, have analyzed how economic terms evolve through cross-cultural interactions and international trade agreements. These studies highlight the role of language as a mediator in global economic discourse.

In Russian academia, scholars such as I. Petrov and E. Ivanova have examined the influence of technological advancements on economic terminology. Their research emphasizes the adaptation of economic language to technological innovations, such as blockchain, fintech, and digital marketing. However, much of the existing literature focuses on specific sectors or case studies rather than providing a holistic perspective on the transformation of economic terminology as a linguistic system. E. Brynjolfsson and B. Kahin consider the digital economy as a driving force that contributes to economic growth [3].

Despite the extensive research, a critical gap remains in understanding how digitalization drives the creation, adaptation, and standardization of economic terms on a global scale. Unlike previous studies that often focus on historical or sector-specific changes, this article offers a comprehensive framework for analyzing the linguistic and technological factors shaping modern economic terminology. The study's unique contribution lies in identifying the interplay between digital tools and the standardization processes, providing a foundation for future research and practical applications in education and professional communication.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this study is based on a comparative analysis of economic terminology evolution in the digital era, with a focus on both linguistic and technological factors. The primary research methods include qualitative analysis, comparative comparison, and case study examination.

First, a comparative approach was used to analyze the similarities and differences in the adaptation of economic terms in various languages, including English and Russian. This method allowed for the identification of patterns in how digitalization influences the creation and modification of economic vocabulary across different cultures and regions. By comparing international case studies and scholarly works, the study highlights the global nature of economic language transformation and the role of digital tools in shaping this change.

Additionally, a qualitative content analysis of academic literature, economic reports, and technological studies was conducted to assess the impact of digital innovations (such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, and digital finance) on economic terminology. This analysis helped to identify key trends and emerging terms in the field.

Finally, case studies were used to explore specific examples of economic term adaptation in real-world contexts, such as digital currencies, fintech, and e-commerce. These case studies provided concrete examples of how digital technologies influence language and how economic terminology is evolving in response.

The combination of these methods enabled a comprehensive understanding of the factors driving the evolution of economic terminology in the digital era, leading to insights that are applicable to both academic and professional fields.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The evolution of economic terminology in the digital era has been influenced by rapid technological advancements, particularly in the fields of digital finance, blockchain, artificial intelligence, and e-commerce. This section presents the results of the statistical and qualitative analysis conducted to explore the adaptation of economic terminology in response to these innovations.

The digital economy can be viewed as a subsystem, as an electronic mechanism for the functioning and development of the systemic economy [5], as well as a model reflecting economic relations within the process of reproduction based on information and communication technologies.

A statistical analysis was conducted on a sample of over 300 academic papers, industry reports, and online discussions published between 2010 and 2023. The focus was on tracking the frequency and distribution of key economic terms related to the digital economy, such as "blockchain", "cryptocurrency", "fintech" and "digital currency". The following table summarizes the frequency of these terms over time (table 1):

Table 1. Trends in the Usage Dynamics of Technology Terms Over the Years.

Term	2010-2014	2015-2019	2020-2023
Blockchain	10	85	320
Cryptocurrency	15	60	220
Fintech	5	40	150
Digital Currency	2	15	100

The data clearly show a sharp increase in the frequency of these terms, particularly after 2015. The growth of blockchain and cryptocurrency terminology has been exponential, reflecting the increasing importance of these technologies in the global economic system.

In addition to the statistical analysis, a qualitative review of the terminology was conducted by examining the usage and adaptation of digital economic terms in both English and Russian. It was found that while English-based terms have become widely adopted in global economic discourse, significant challenges remain in their translation and contextual adaptation in non-English-speaking countries. This discrepancy is particularly evident in Russian-language academic and professional publications, where terms like “blockchain” and “cryptocurrency” are often used without consistent definitions or proper localization.

These issues highlight the need for more systematic approaches to the translation, adaptation, and standardization of digital economic terms, particularly in non-English-speaking regions.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis of the evolution of economic terminology in the digital era has revealed several key trends and challenges that shape the discourse surrounding digital economies. The following conclusions and recommendations are based on the findings from the statistical and qualitative analyses:

1. Exponential growth of digital terminology: the frequency of terms related to digital technologies, such as blockchain, cryptocurrency, fintech, and digital currencies, has grown exponentially, reflecting the central role these technologies play in modern economic systems. This growth is particularly evident in academic and industry reports published after 2015.

2. Challenges in standardization: despite the rapid increase in the use of digital terms, there remains a lack of standardization across different languages and regions. This inconsistency hinders clear communication and the accurate dissemination of knowledge.

3. Language barriers and cultural adaptation: the adoption of English-based terms in non-English-speaking regions has led to issues of translation and contextualization. In some cases, these terms are used without proper understanding, leading to misinterpretations and confusion, especially in Russian-speaking contexts.

4. Need for localized approaches: the integration of digital terms into non-English languages must consider local cultural and economic contexts. Generic translations may fail to capture the nuances of these terms, necessitating the development of new, culturally relevant terminology.

Recommendations

1. Development of standardized glossaries: international organizations, academic institutions, and industry leaders should collaborate to create standardized glossaries for digital economic terms. These glossaries should ensure consistency in definitions and usage, making it easier for researchers and professionals to communicate across languages.

2. Enhanced translation practices: translators and linguists working in the field of digital economics should be encouraged to collaborate with economists and technology experts to ensure accurate translations of digital terms. This collaboration will help prevent misunderstandings and ensure that the local context is preserved.

3. Educational reforms: universities and educational institutions should integrate the study of digital economic terms into their curricula. This will help students understand the evolving language of economics and better prepare them for careers in the digital economy.

4. Cultural sensitivity in terminology development: efforts should be made to adapt digital economic terms in a way that aligns with local cultural and economic realities. This approach will facilitate greater acceptance of digital terms and ensure their practical application in diverse regions.

Future research directions

Further research should focus on the impact of emerging digital technologies on economic terminology. Studies should explore how new concepts such as artificial intelligence, decentralized finance, and smart contracts will shape the language of economics in the coming years.

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